

ZILZILAGA CHIDAMLI QURILISHNING ASOSIY TAMOIYILLARI.

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Annatsiya: Ushbu maqolda loyihalash jarayonining boshida bino va inshootlarning yangi konstruktiv sxemalari zilzilaga chidamli qurilish sohasida ixtisoslashgan ilmiy-tadqiqot va loyihalash tashkilotlari mutaxassisleri tomonidan majburiy ekspert tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan ko'rstamalar va tajribalarni sohaga tadbiq etish haqida.

Kalit so'z: Seysmik izolyatsiya, konstruktiv yechim, seysmik yuk, fazoviy ramalar, pasportlashtirish.

Abstract: In this article, at the beginning of the design process, new structural schemes of buildings and structures are used, developed by specialists from research and design organizations specializing in the field of earthquake-resistant construction.

Key words: Seismic isolation, constructive solution, seismic load, spatial frames, certification.

Seysmik izolyatsiya va seysmik yuklarni dinamik tartibga solishning boshqa tizimlaridan foydalanganda ma'lum bir tizimni tanlash, shuningdek hisoblash va loyihalash ixtisoslashtirilgan dizayn va ilmiy tashkilotlar ishtirokida amalga oshirilishi kerak. Zilzilalar va binolarga tutash tuproqlarning tebranishi paytida inshootlarning ishlashi to'g'risida ishonchli ma'lumot olish uchun ommaviy qurilish binolarining o'ziga xos asosiy turlari, tubdan yangi konstruktiv yechimlarga ega binolar, shuningdek, ayniqsa maxsus inshootlar loyihalarida muhandislik-seysmometrik xizmat stantsiyalarini joylashtirishni ta'minlash kerak[1-5].

Qurilish tugagandan so'ng obyektlarni pasportlashtirish, shuningdek mavjud obyektlarni tekshirish va pasportlashtirish seysmik hududlarda foydalaniladigan sanoat va fuqarolik binolari (inshootlari) ning texnik holatini baholash va pasportlashtirish bo'yicha amaldagi me'yoriy hujjatlarga muvofiq amalga oshirilishi kerak. Ko'p qavatli karkazli binolarda gorizontal seysmik yukni sezadigan tizim qattiq ramka tugunlari bo'lgan fazoviy rama bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin; seysmik yukni idrok etishda ishtirok etadigan plomba bilan qattiq rama tugunlari bo'lgan fazoviy rama; vertikal bog'lanishlar, diafragma yoki qattqlik yadrolari bo'lgan rama; kesilmagan rama [6-17].

Katta panelli binolar uzellari va ko'ndalang yuk ko'taruvchi devorlar bilan loyihalashtirilishi kerak. Transvers va bo'ylama devorlar shiftlar va qoplamalar bilan birgalikda seysmik yuklarni sezadigan yagona fazoviy tizimni hosil qiladi. Rejadagi tashqi devorlarning proektsiyalari 3 m dan oshmasligi kerak, devor va zamin panellari, qoida tariqasida, xonaning kattaligi bilan ta'minlanishi kerak. Ko'ndalang devorlarning keng qadamlari (4,2 m dan ortiq) bo'lgan binolarda bir-biriga bog'langan ikkita elementdan pol panellariga ruxsat beriladi. Devor panellarini mustahkamlash fazoviy ramalar yoki mustahkamlovchi mashlar shaklida ikki tomonlama amalga oshirilishi kerak. Panelning har bir tekisligiga o'rnatilgan vertikal va gorizontal armaturaning maydoni devorning tegishli qismining kamida 0,025% bo'lishi kerak[10-17].

Hisoblangan seysmiklik 7 va 8 ball bilan tashqi tosh devorlar va ichki temir-beton yoki po'lat ramalardan (ustunlardan) foydalanishga ruxsat beriladi. Bunday holda, toshli binolar uchun belgilangan talablar bajarilishi kerak. Bunday binolarning balandligi 7 m dan oshmasligi kerak. Monolit binolar, odatda, yuk ko'taruvchi (asosan og'ir beton) yoki yuk ko'tarmaydigan tashqi devorlari bo'lgan o'zaro faoliyat devor tizimi sifatida loyihalashtirilishi kerak.

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